

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D5.3 – UP2030 SERVICE PLATFORM

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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Abstract	The purpose of this document is to present the UP2030 Service Platform, a key instrument of the project. The platform focuses on the concept of upscaling and aims to provide cities with a space where they can find methods and solutions to help them increase the impact and ensure the continuity of the pilot projects they have developed, focusing mainly on overcoming barriers related to governmental and financial aspects. The platform is aimed at both cities that have participated in the project and those that have not.			

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Executive summary

The purpose of this report is to present the UP2030 Service Platform, which is one of the main instruments developed as part of the project's upscaling activities. This document defines the framework in which the platform has been developed, following the 5UP methodology, continuing the work carried out in cities in previous phases of the project, and proposing solutions that reinforce the impact generated by the prototypes.

The following sections of the report provide information about the specific objectives addressed by the UP2030 Service Platform, as well as the design followed to build its structure. It also presents the four main tools contained in the platform and how they help to meet the established objectives. These tools are:

- Urban Typologies.
- Transformative Governance Tool.
- Cost and Benefit Analysis (CBA) Guide.
- Green Finance Guide.

These tools have played a fundamental role in designing an upscaling plan for the [prototypes](#) (pilot projects) developed by the UP2030 cities. The platform draws on these tools and the upscaling methodology developed in the project to guide cities through this upscaling process. The platform aims to be a practical guide, teaching how to apply theoretical concepts in real cases, and to this end it contains a specific section where users can find real cases where an upscaling plan has been designed, following the methodology and tools mentioned above. For this reason, this document also contains a section detailing how the upscaling phase was designed in UP2030 and the results obtained by each city.

Finally, the efforts made and planned to promote and increase the impact of the platform are mentioned, with the aim of ensuring the use and operation of the platform beyond the conclusion date of the UP2030 project.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the Work Packages (WPs) structure. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment with adelphi, Global Green Growth Institute, GreenAdapt, UIC, Fraunhofer and R-Cities, together with the cities and their liaisons, and WPs 2, 3, 4 and 6. The following table lists the deliverables and milestones that were input for this present document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content here presented.

Table 1: List of deliverables that D5.3 takes input from and contributes to.

Input from	Contributes to
D2.1 – The 5UP approach and its contextualisation in the project cities.	D5.7 – Online Learning Programme materials.
D3.1, D3.2 and D3.3 – Transformative pathways roadmaps: strategic integration of solutions and interoperability 1, 2 and 3.	D6.9 – Exploitation & Sustainability Planning & Activities Report 2.
D4.1 and D4.2 – UP2030 implementation plan for the pilot cities 1 and 2.	D6.12 – Sharing UP2030 best practices and policy briefs with the Mission’s Platform.

<p>D4.3 – Sustained engagement strategy of Learning & Action Alliances to promote the neutrality vision in the UP2030 pilots.</p> <p>D5.1 and D5.2 – Analysis and recommendations for transformative governance and policy 1 and 2.</p> <p>D5.4 and D5.5 – Guidelines for economic valuations & assessment of financial instruments for spatial interventions 1 and 2.</p> <p>D5.6 – Learning Programme Design, Development and Sustainability.</p> <p>D5.7 – Online Learning Programme materials.</p>	
<p>Mil.4 – Cities have set-up LAAs.</p> <p>Mil.5 – Cities run first workshop on needs.</p> <p>Mil.6 – Cities run second workshop on vision.</p> <p>Mil.7 – Cities establish user stories.</p> <p>Mil.10 – Cities run third workshop on action.</p> <p>Mil.13 – All cities have at least one successful prototype.</p> <p>Mil.14 – Cities run fourth workshop on upscale.</p> <p>Mil.15 – Training programme successful delivery completed.</p>	<p>Mil.15 – Training programme successful delivery completed.</p> <p>Mil.16 – Service platform up operative.</p>

The primary beneficiaries of this deliverable are cities and their local municipalities, as well as practitioners engaged in urban planning, governance and climate-neutral transformation processes. The Service Platform is intended to support cities when assessing opportunities for upscaling, offering a structured set of tools for cities initiating or expanding similar processes in the future. This deliverable, and consequently the Service Platform, will be shared and disseminated not only through UP2030’s main channels, such as social media and newsletter, but also via [Zenodo](#). Additionally, dissemination can be reinforced through webinars, conference presentations and partners’ own communication channels, ensuring broad visibility and long-term usability of the Service Platform.

Acronyms

Table 2: List of milestones that D5.3 takes input from and contributes to.

Acronym	Full name
CBA	Cost and Benefit Analysis
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
ICLEI	International Council for Local Environmental Initiatives
GGGI	Global Green Growth Institute
LAA	Learning and Action Alliance
Mil	Milestone
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NUTS	Nomenclature des Unités Territoriales Statistiques
UIC	Universitat Internacional de Catalunya
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

The purpose of this document is to present the UP2030 Service Platform, one of the key outputs of the project's upscaling activities under Work Package 5 (WP5). The document outlines the conceptual framework guiding the platform's development, describes its structure and components and explains how it supports cities in advancing the concepts designed throughout UP2030. It covers both the tools included in the platform and the methodologies that support them, with a particular focus on one of the key steps of the 5UP approach, the upscaling.

The Service Platform has been conceived as an instrument to strengthen the *enabling environment* for climate-neutral, resilient and just urban development. In this context, the enabling environment refers to the governance conditions, institutional arrangements, financial frameworks and knowledge resources that allow cities to expand project ideas, embed them in policy processes and maximise their long-term impact. The platform compiles tools specifically designed to support these enabling dimensions, helping cities move from isolated pilot actions to strategic, city-wide transformations.

Figure 1: Summary of the three pillars of the enabling environment.

This deliverable therefore provides a comprehensive overview of the platform, its target users, its connections with previous UP2030 activities and the mechanisms through which it is expected to generate value both during and beyond the lifetime of the project. The Service Platform is available under the following domain: <https://urbanplanningfor2030.eu/>

1.2 Document structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 – Introduction: description of the purpose and scope of the document and its structure.
- ❖ Section 2 – Objective of the UP2030 Service Platform: definition of the goals to be achieved with the development of the platform, including an explanation of its structure, partners involved and list of beneficiaries.
- ❖ Section 3 – Connections with previous activities of UP2030. References to other methodologies and resources developed in the project, indicating the connections between these resources and the Service Platform.
- ❖ Section 4 – Tools of the UP2030 Service Platform. Summary of the tools included in the platform, providing the list of objectives they aim to meet, its structure and the obtained results.

- ❖ Section 5 – Connections with the UP2030 Upscaling Methodology. Alignment with the activities that have been conducted with the UP2030 pilot cities under the upscale phase of the project.
- ❖ Section 6 – Dissemination and exploitation of the UP2030 Service Platform. List of dissemination activities conducted and planned, as well as opportunities for collaboration and exploitation after the project ends.
- ❖ Section 7 – Conclusion. Reflection on the main results obtained, and vision for the future.

2 Objective of the UP2030 Service Platform

2.1 General objectives

The Platform is not merely a repository of solutions developed during the project. In line with the objectives of the project, the UP2030 Service Platform aims to support cities and urban districts in designing and implementing innovative approaches to climate neutrality, urban resilience and spatial justice, by providing different tools and methods that were developed and tested by the cities during the project.

During the first year of the project, work was undertaken to define the structure and objectives of the platform to be provided, based on the working structure to be followed with the cities and the contributions that each partner would make to the project. Each city participating in UP2030 encountered unique challenges and objectives at the project's inception, which were addressed through the implementation of the 5UP methodology. The primary outcome of the project has been the prototypes, i.e. project ideas that can be implemented in the city and contribute to urban transformation, following the three pillars mentioned above (climate neutrality, urban resilience and spatial justice).

Based on this work and taking into account the consortium's extensive experience in this type of project, it was expressed that there is a need to find ways for the prototypes to have a lasting impact after the UP2030 project ends. This is not an easy task due to various barriers that may be encountered. In line with this objective, the UP2030 Service Platform has adopted the concept of 'upscaling' as a reference point, which is one of the steps included in the 5UP approach. The platform aims to provide a space where cities can identify solutions and real-world examples of how project ideas can be upscaled.

The concept of upscaling has been defined as the ability to effectively expand or adapt policies, programs or projects, in different places and over time, to reach more people and have a wider impact. To achieve this, an upscaling methodology was defined in the UP2030 project, which helped cities in setting long-term objectives for their prototypes and define actions for extending the area of impact in their cities. The UP2030 Service Platform collects the tools and strategies that were used by cities in the upscale phase of the project to refine their governance and financial frameworks.

2.1.1 Structure of the UP2030 Service Platform

The platform is structured in three main sections:

- The first part provides the user with an introductory explanation, setting the objectives of the platform, defining the basic concepts about upscaling and how the platform contributes to it, and connecting it with the 5UP methodology (see Section 3 for more details).
- The second section is the central piece of the platform, as it brings the tools that can support cities on upscaling by addressing their governance and financial dimensions.
- The last section shows cities' experiences on upscaling in the UP2030 project. It introduces to the upscaling methodology that was developed and implemented in UP2030 by the pilot cities, and presents the main results obtained by the cities in transferability packages. In this way, the user can find some practical guidance on how to conduct an upscaling plan for its own context, supported by real examples.

The following diagram summarises the content of the UP2030 Service Platform and guides the user on how to navigate through the different sections:

Figure 2: Diagram that indicates the user how to navigate through the different sections of the platform.

2.2 Partners involved

The development of the UP2030 Service Platform was a collaborative effort, as it collects the results of the work done by the following partners:

- ICLEI, responsible for hosting the platform, integrating the content and lead coordination with partners.
- Adelphi, responsible for developing the Transformative Governance tool and co-creating the content and methodology for the Urban Typologies.
- GreenAdapt, responsible for co-creating the content and methodology for the Urban Typologies.
- Global Green Growth Institute, responsible for developing the Cost and Benefit Analysis (CBA) Guide and the Green Finance Guide.
- Fraunhofer IAO, responsible for co-developing the 5UP-Tool.
- Resilient Cities Network, responsible for co-developing the 5UP-Tool.

2.3 Beneficiaries

The UP2030 Service Platform is designed for a wide range of users engaged in urban planning, policy-making and climate action, including:

- Urban planners and municipal administration officers seeking practical tools for climate-neutral urban planning.
- NGOs and local organisations involved in urban development and community engagement.
- Private companies interested in contributing to sustainable city solutions.
- Consultants and advisors working on urban transformation projects.
- Neighbourhood associations advocating for community-driven changes in their urban spaces.
- Financing institutions looking to support sustainable urban development.
- Academics and students who want to learn through research-driven methodologies (MOOC and case studies).

The Platform is primarily designed for actors who have already developed a pilot project and are seeking solutions to help them upscale it, with the objective of making a greater and more lasting impact over time. For users who do not yet have a project idea, the platform also offers resources to guide them in developing one, following the 5UP methodology tested during the UP2030 project. Further details on this can be found in the Section 3.

3 Connections with previous activities of UP2030

As mentioned before, the UP2030 Service Platform is strongly linked to the upscaling objectives of the project. The upscaling component is the last phase of the implementation methodology followed by the pilot cities in the project, as defined in Deliverables 4.1 (D4.1) (Kapetas, Liakou, & Tajuddin, D4.1 - UP2030 Implementation plan for the pilot cities 1, 2023) and D4.2 (Kapetas, Aili, & Tajuddin, D4.2 - UP2030 Implementation plan for the pilot cities 2, 2023). Each step centred upon a workshop designed to engage stakeholders and communities in the planning and design of the pilot. This ensured diverse contributions towards the city’s climate neutrality objectives.

Figure 3: Implementation methodology at the pilot environments run through participation activities.

The upscale phase was designed following the results and methodologies obtained in the previous phases (Analysis, Vision and Action). The main objective was to analyse the prototypes that were defined in the action phase by the pilot cities and explore opportunities for city-wide implementation potential. The upscaling methodology that was designed for this phase is explained in detail in Section 5.

3.1 Alignment with the 5UP Methodology – 5UP Workbook

The UP2030 Service Platform, as it supports upscaling, contributes to the 5UP methodology. The Service Platform provides cities with instruments and resources that support cities to identify needs and define actions for upscaling their project ideas, by addressing key dimensions such as governance and finance.

For users who have not yet a developed project idea, the platform offers guidance for developing one through following the 5UP methodology implemented during UP2030 (see Figure 4 for more information). Instructions on how to apply the 5UP approach are contained in the 5UP Workbook, developed by Fraunhofer and Resilient Cities Network, which will be hosted on the platform.

Figure 4: Steps of the 5UP methodology.

This workbook, developed in an excel file format, collects the results and processes from the three years collaboration with the 47 consortium partners, working together to address the socio-technical transitions that cities must navigate on the path to climate neutrality, resilience and social justice. The workbook is aligned with the audience of the Service Platform, as it is directed to the cities that:

- Have climate neutrality on the urban planning agenda.
- Have a problem statement / challenge that would like to explore solutions for.
- Have project ideas ready for implementation.
- Want to assess how its city functions and explore alternative approaches.
- Want to ensure that no one is left behind in the transition to climate neutrality.
- Aim to shift from a project-based approach to a strategy driven model that provides a broader perspective on specific actions.
- Aim to upscale your project ideas.

The workbook contains a dedicated tab for each of the UP phases, where the user can find detailed information on the requirement for the execution of each step, as well as key resources that played a role in each phase. In addition, it showcases examples of UP2030 cities who have applied this framework, so users can find real-world examples on how a city can implement the methodology's different steps and how the obtained results look like. Furthermore, an editable section is provided, so that users of the workbook can add useful information for their own context.

3.2 [Massive Online Open Course \(MOOC\)](#)

In addition to the UP2030 Service Platform, another important instrument developed in WP5 is the MOOC developed by UIC, titled "How to Build Carbon Neutral, Resilient and Just Cities". This is hosted on the e-learning platform of the Urban Resilience Research Network.

The course has been created to bridge the gap between scientific advancements, climate governance and planning. The primary aim is to empower city practitioners with the knowledge, skills, and tools necessary for integrating the principles of carbon neutrality, climate resilience, and spatial justice into their urban planning practices. Structured into five modules, the learning program is organised around the 5UP approach to resonate with the project's goals and to capitalize on the diverse outcomes of the UP2030 project. The training program consists of highly comprehensive video capsules and its structure encompasses a methodical curriculum covering theoretical foundations, technical aspects, and case studies. More details about the content and structure of the MOOC can be found in D5.7.

The MOOC complements the Service Platform to build capacity in cities by providing them with information about the theoretical concepts, tools, methodologies and case studies that have been developed and implemented during the project. To develop these two instruments, ICLEI and UIC have worked in continuous collaboration since the beginning of the project to ensure that both platforms are aligned with the objective of WP5 and the project in general. There are also connections between the two instruments, as the Service Platform provides links and indications of where users can find more information in the MOOC about certain concepts, tools and results included in the platform.

4 Tools of the UP2030 Service Platform

This section presents the tools that are hosted in the Service Platform. These tools address the main components of the enabling environment and constitute the central axis of the platform. For their integration, ICLEI worked in close collaboration with the different tool providers, who developed a first version of the tool on a specific format (for instance, GGGI developed its tools in an Excel format) that was then taken by ICLEI to develop the online version of the tools.

The following sub-sections provide the definition and objectives of each tool, together with an overview of their structure and the main results generated. Further information about the tools can be found in the UP2030 Service Platform, under the [“Tools” section](#).

4.1 Urban Typologies

4.1.1 Definition and objectives

Urban Typologies tool is an interactive map providing a framework for exploring the diverse characteristics of European regions at NUTS-3 level, based on features related to urban planning, climate change mitigation, and adaptation. By grouping European cities and regions with similar attributes, the Urban Typologies aim to support these areas in identifying relevant strategies for achieving climate neutrality and resilience.

The Urban Typologies have the following objectives:

- Identify similarities between regions to foster collaboration.
- Encourage knowledge-sharing and communication for more effective solutions, especially between regions and cities sharing similar opportunities and challenges.
- Support urban planners and decision-makers in tackling climate change by identifying key challenges, opportunities and action areas with high relevance for future measures in specific clusters.

The typologies were created using a well-established methodology with a cluster analysis at its core. The cluster analysis is a statistical method. It groups units, in this case NUTS-3 units, based on similarities, so shared numerical characteristics. The reason an analysis at a very fine scale (i.e., cities only) was not conducted was due to the lack of data availability. As an alternative, the NUTS-3 level was selected. The NUTS (Nomenclature des Unités Territoriales Statistiques, or “Classification of Territorial Units for Statistics”, in English) classification divides the EU into hierarchical levels, with NUTS-3 being the most detailed. It is a well-established standard unit of analysis used for the development of EU regional policies and socio-economic analysis. Using NUTS-3 as scale of analysis provides multiple benefits:

- The NUTS-3 regions integrate existing administrative boundaries, meaning that the findings are more directly relevant to policy makers.
- It allows cross-border comparisons of urban trends.
- It ensures consistent data availability across European regions.

The study area includes NUTS-3 regions that part of the EU27, in addition to the NUTS-3 regions of Belfast and Istanbul, thanks to the data provided by the cities. Excluded from the study area are the French Overseas Territories, Azores and Madeira, Canary Islands and Spanish autonomous regions of Ceuta and Melilla.

4.1.2 Structure of the tool

Four different Urban Typologies have been created to analyse the characteristics of different NUTS-3 level regions at the European level:

- Contributions to Mitigation – It identifies areas according to the primary sources of CO₂ emissions and their potential for renewable energy deployment.
- Capacity for Action – It includes socio-economic and demographic indicators, grouping cities based on the resources and capacities they can mobilise for adaptation or mitigation measures.
- Climate Hazards – This typology uses environmental risk and exposure indicators to cluster regions facing similar climate-related threats.
- Urban Morphology – It captures the structural characteristics of urban areas within the regions, grouping regions with comparable spatial and built environments.

The typologies were created using a well-established methodology with a cluster analysis at its core. These typologies consist of five to nine clusters each, based on a [list of indicators and processing steps](#) that was used in the data analysis process. The following table provides a list of all the clusters that have been created in this data analysis:

Table 3: List of clusters created within each typology.

Typologies	Clusters
1. Contributions to Mitigation.	Carbon sinks and wind power potential in northern Scandinavia.
	High potential for renewables and high CO ₂ emissions.
	High potential for renewables and lower CO ₂ emissions
	Very high renewable energy potentials and very low sectoral emissions in southern Europe.
	PV as the sole potential in highly urbanized small cluster.
	High solar power potential, low sectoral emissions in southern continental Europe
	High industrial emissions and average renewables potential
	Highest wind potential in contiguous European lowlands
2. Capacity for Action.	Remote regions with Large Vulnerable Age Groups.
	Moderately Urban Western European Regions

	Touristic Destinations
	Developing economies with high environmental value
	Strong Economic Centers
	Moderately Urbanized and Transitional Regions
3. Climate Hazards.	Wet conditions and low heat stress in northern latitudes.
	Extreme flooding and sea-level rise exposure in urbanized low-lying coastal areas.
	Complex hazard combination in low-lying central Europe.
	Heat hazard and air pollution in lowlands and basins in southern and eastern Europe.
	Wetter conditions with landslide and flooding in mountainous regions
	Complex hazard combination in low mountains in central Europe
	Greatest heat hazard, and wildfire risk in dry southern Europe climate
	Highest exposure to flooding in pockets of Europe
4. Urban Morphology.	Most pronounced dryness, alongside high heat hazard and wildfire, in southern Europe
	Flat urban-industrial hubs with low green coverage.
	Moderate-density regions with open spaces.
	Steep urban profile with ample green spaces and little industry.
	Very steep urban profile with extensive green spaces and little industry.
High-density urban centres with minimal open space.	

To understand the adaptation opportunities and challenges unique to each cluster, it was essential to examine how clusters differ from and relate to one another. The average indicator values were compared and their spread across clusters were analysed to identify defining characteristics. In addition, the geographical distribution was also considered, which often revealed spatial patterns and added contextual insights beyond the data. Together, these elements helped build clear profiles of each cluster, highlighting their unique traits and interrelationships.

Each typology and cluster is displayed in an interactive map, as it is shown in Figure 5:

Figure 5: Example view of the interactive map with the "Contributions to Mitigation" typology selected, displaying regional variations in mitigation potential across Europe. Each cluster is represented by a different colour.

Each typology and each of its clusters can be displayed on the map, and the different typologies can be selected by clicking on its title on the map page. Each map consists of the regions which belong to a specific cluster, as well as the clusters constituting the typology displayed. For each typology, the interactive map visualizes:

- Spatial distribution of clusters across Europe.
- Basic cluster descriptions ("overview") for each cluster.
- Interpretation of key characteristics, in form of common challenges, opportunities and suggestions for action areas and solutions, for each cluster. In addition, for each indicator a table under "indicator values" provides a clicked region's actual values, the means of the cluster it is in and the means over all regions in the typology.

4.1.3 Results

The Urban Typologies provide a robust framework for exploring the diverse characteristics of European regions, particularly regarding climate resilience and potential pathways to net-zero. They enable regions and cities with similar opportunities and challenges to recognise one another, fostering connections, collaboration and mutual learning. Each typology highlights common challenges and opportunities within its clusters, as well as key areas for action. In doing so, the framework empowers urban planners and decision-makers to identify strategic priorities and address climate challenges more effectively.

These results are aligned with the 5UP approach for strategic climate planning, being particularly beneficial in the following UP phases:

- **UPdate:** the tool helps cities determine which cluster they belong to, provides a starting point for needs assessment and identifies regions with similar challenges to encourage collaboration.
- **UPscale:** Urban Typologies helps cities expand climate strategies by identifying potential barriers and solutions. In addition, it supports net-zero and climate-resilient city transitions.
- **UPTake:** it enables targeted dissemination of best practices and strengthens collaboration between cities in the same cluster.

4.2 Transformative Governance Tool

4.2.1 Definition and objectives

The Transformative Governance Tool is a self-assessment framework for cities to evaluate and enhance their governance structures, enabling stronger institutional arrangements for urban transformation. The objective of this questionnaire-based self-assessment tool is to help city administrations evaluate their governance structures, analyse the strengths and gaps in the current governance setup and identify areas for improvement in climate and urban policy. Based on the assessment, tailored recommendations are provided to guide improvements and foster progress in these areas.

This tool is directed to a varied range of actors: city officials and urban planners, to evaluate governance readiness; policymakers, to identify gaps in governance arrangements; and multi-stakeholder teams, ensuring inclusive governance processes. By addressing different components of transformative governance, which refers to the norms, institutions and processes used by cities to make and implement decisions to move towards climate neutrality and liveability, the tool responds to the following purposes:

- Assess and improve governance structures for urban transformation.
- Align governance frameworks with climate neutrality goals.
- Support decision-making for urban policymakers and planners.
- Enhance coordination across multiple governance levels.

4.2.2 Structure of the tool

The central piece of the tool is the questionnaire, where users are able to score their governance structures across five dimensions, answering multiple-choice questions (0-4 scale). Each question of the questionnaire includes an explanation that helps the user to provide an accurate score. The governance dimensions that are assessed are the following:

- **Goals and perspectives:** setting strategic transformation objectives.
- **Instruments and strategies:** implementing regulatory and policy tools.

- Levels and scales: ensuring multi-level coordination.
- Actors and networks: engaging diverse stakeholders.
- Responsibilities and resources: allocating institutional and financial capacity.

The initial version of the questionnaire was developed in a Microsoft Word document, which was then transformed into an online form, as shown in Figure 6:

1. Goals & Perspectives

1.1. Are the goals and objectives regarding your task well-developed?

- 0: Goals for the area of action do not exist or are unclear, so no meaningful action is possible.
- 1: Some goals exist but are defined poorly. The goals are not clear, or it is not clear how to go about achieving them. Action is stalled.
- 2: Some goals and objectives are set and SMART, but it is not a comprehensive picture. This enables action that meets basic standards.
- 3: Many goals and objectives are set and SMART. Action advances effectively in many aspects.
- 4: Most goals and objectives are set and SMART. Action advances effectively.

1.2 Does current political action take a comprehensive perspective on your task?

- 0: The task is only seen from one perspective, or the question of different components and perspectives has never been considered.
- 1: There is some understanding of different perspectives of the task, but no explicit analysis or assessment of these perspectives.
- 2: There is some explicit consideration of different perspectives of the task, e.g. with one instrument or in a process between different actors.
- 3: There is explicit consideration of different perspectives of the task, through an effective instrument or process that has been established specifically to achieve this.
- 4: There is an elaborate instrument or process established to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the task in question, considering a wide array of perspectives on a permanent basis.

1.3. Does setting the goals and objectives include an appropriate procedure to consider different groups of the population?

- 0: Different population groups are not at all a topic when goals and objectives for the task are set.
- 1: Different population groups are mentioned when goals and objectives for the task are set.
- 2: Implications for the different population are discussed in some detail when goals and objectives for the task are set.
- 3: Implications for the different population are discussed substantially when goals and objectives for the are set; there is a specific process for this (e.g. assessment).
- 4: Implications for the different population groups are discussed profoundly when goals and objectives for the task are set, there is a specific process, and this aspect is monitored.

Figure 6: Overview of the self-assessment questionnaire of the Transformative Governance Tool.

Based on the answers given to the questions, the user is directed to the results page, where low-scoring areas can be identified and governance improvements can be prioritized. Furthermore, the tool contains an extended list of recommendations that cities could follow in order to develop a governance action plan, classified in 11 different dimensions. Based on the results obtained, the tool highlights the governance dimensions that are more relevant for the user in order to address its governance challenges.

For each of the 11 recommendations dimensions, a definition of the type of recommendation is provided, together with examples from UP2030 project, list of materials that supports the adoption of this recommendation, and best practices from different projects and initiatives. Figure 7 shows how a recommendation dimension looks like:

5. Cater to Vulnerable and Under-Represented Groups ^

For every public action, it is key to identify population groups that are especially **vulnerable** and/or **underrepresented** (e.g. elderly, low-income, people with disabilities, minorities). These groups tend to overlap but might also be different, e.g. while elderly people might be more vulnerable, their perspectives and needs might be well-represented and understood, while it might be the other way around for migrant communities. The **Impacts of envisioned actions on different population groups** should be systematically assessed, with particular attention to vulnerable communities. This is a basis to analyse what an equitable distribution of benefits looks like (it might mean some groups need more attention or a different approach) and helps prevent unintended negative consequences.

When planning your task, it might be useful to establish **specific procedures** of including diverse perspectives to make sure the differentiated impacts remain on your radar. For this, consider ways to involve these groups throughout the process, systematically and on a regular basis. Methods can encompass direct participation such as participatory budgeting, community workshops, focus groups, online consultations, written feedback, or alternative methods (usually less resource-intensive) such as customer journey mapping, persona-method, social impact assessments, representative surveys. Choose **suitable formats** depending on the process phase and the input needed: direct engagement (focus group discussions, community forums, regular consultations, co-creating formats), representative input (advocacy group meetings, feedback from social service providers), research (e.g. questionnaires, interviews).

UP2030 tools on inclusive participation and social justice v

Helpful material v

Best practices v

Figure 7: Example of a recommendation provided by the Transformative Governance Tool.

4.2.3 Results

As a summary, the user can get three main outcomes from the Transformative Governance Tool:

- A structured self-assessment questionnaire that evaluates governance across five dimensions.
- Actionable recommendations on how to improve governance structures for upscaling transformative solutions.
- A flexible tool that can be used at different stages of urban planning and for various policy areas.

The Transformative Governance Tool aligns with the 5UP methodology by supporting cities in identifying gaps and strengths in their governance structures. It is particularly relevant during the following UP phases:

- **UPdate:** the tool identifies governance strengths and areas that need improvement.
- **Upscale:** the tool ensures governance frameworks are in place before expanding urban projects or policies.

It can also be used in any governance context where improvements are needed, especially when setting up or expanding urban sustainability projects.

4.3 [Cost and Benefit Analysis Guide](#)

4.3.1 [Definition and objectives](#)

The CBA Guide is a structured approach to assessing the economic viability of climate projects, ensuring municipalities can build strong business cases for interventions. The Guide supports cities in identifying appropriate tools to assess the costs and benefits of various climate interventions. It draws on a curated collection of open-access CBA tools and helps users find the ones most relevant to their project context. In particular, the CBA Guide is intended for the following types of users:

- Urban planners and city administrators, to evaluate financial feasibility of projects.
- Financial and economic analysts, to conduct in-depth CBA for climate interventions.
- Project developers and consultants, to strengthen investment cases.

Through a short set of guiding questions, users are guided to suitable tools based on key project characteristics, needs and resource availabilities. Based on user responses, the tool recommends a first-best and second-best CBA tool. Supporting documents and data sources are also provided in the Guide to help cities move forward with implementation.

The content of this Guide is based on a literature review and analysis of publicly available CBA tools, conducted by Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI). The algorithm developed to select the most suitable CBA tools is based on a scoring system where the tools included in the Guide get the more scores the better they match the criteria chosen by the user. Additionally, the Guide provides links to relevant data sources as well as guides and case studies, to support users in applying the selected CBA tool effectively.

4.3.2 [Structure of the tool](#)

The main component of the tool is the CBA questionnaire that users need to answer in order to obtain the CBA tools that best fit their needs. More specific answers will result in more tailored recommendations. All questions need to be answered by making drop-down selections. To receive both a first-best and second-best tool recommendation, users must complete all selections, including the two resource-related questions at the bottom. Each filter corresponds to one of the following guiding questions for the user:

- What do you want to do?
- Are you interested in mitigation or adaptation projects?
- Which sector would you like to focus on in your activity?
- What benefits would you like to include in the CBA?
- What type of national or local data do you have available?
- What resources are you going to use for the activity?
- What is the amount of your resources available for the activity?

The CBA Guide was first developed in an Excel-based format by GGGI. In order to integrate it in the UP2030 Service Platform, ICLEI and GGGI worked in close collaboration, trying to make the tool as most user-friendly as possible. Figure 8 shows the current version of the questionnaire that has been created in the UP2030 Service Platform.

CBA Guide

What do you want to do? ?

- Getting more familiar with the topic of CBA
- Light approach to CBA for a rough overview of costs and benefits of my project
- Detailed CBA

Are you interested in mitigation or adaptation projects? ?

- Mitigation
- Adaptation
- Mitigation and adaptation

Which sector would you like to focus on in your activity? ?

- Transport
- Buildings
- Waste management
- Urban parks
- Agriculture
- Industry
- Energy

What benefits would you like to include in the CBA? Please select up to 3 options per category, as applicable. ?

- Health
- Environment
- Cost savings
- Economic and social

What resources are you going to use for the activity? ?

- Internal resources by dedicating staff time
- External resources by mandating an expert

Submit

Figure 8: Overview of the questionnaire of the CBA Guide.

Once all fields are selected, the recommended tools will automatically appear in the green-highlighted "First-best tool" and "Second-best tool" table. The Guide offers an overview of the recommended tools under the questionnaire. In addition, this Guide highlights key data needs as per the recommended tools (based on previous answers – sector, selected benefits, etc.), listing the types of data required. If key data is not readily available in the municipality, the Guide suggests sources (both within the guide and externally) to support cities. The links and data tables provided in the Guide are for guidance purposes. Users must consult each tool's documentation for exact requirements and ensure all data used is local, current and fit for purpose.

4.3.3 Results

The CBA Guide enables cities to identify the most appropriate CBA tools for their projects, ensuring a comprehensive assessment of economic, environmental and social impacts. The results provided by the tool support on building:

- A clear framework for assessing both tangible and intangible benefits of climate projects.
- Stronger business cases for climate projects, improving their chances of securing funding.
- A clearer understanding of the economic and societal impact of interventions.

The Guide is particularly useful in the planning and evaluation stages of climate projects, contributing to the following UP phases:

- UPdate: the guide supports initial cost-benefit evaluations during project development.

- Upscale: the guide assists in evaluating financial feasibility when expanding successful interventions.

4.4 [Green Finance Guide](#)

4.4.1 [Definition and objectives](#)

The Green Finance Guide provides cities with a comprehensive overview of financial instruments and mechanisms across various sectors and stages of project development to support sustainable urban projects. Its objective is to help municipalities navigate green funding options, ensuring they can access, combine and apply innovative financing solutions for effective climate action. The Guide has been designed to:

- Inform municipalities about a wide range of available financial instruments.
- Offer high-level guidance on how to blend or sequence these instruments.
- Highlight key stakeholders involved in the provision of climate finance.
- Showcase real-world examples of how instruments have been successfully applied.
- Provide access to relevant financing and technical assistance programmes across Europe.

Within the municipalities, the Guide is particularly intended for the following actors:

- City financial departments, to identify the best green financing options.
- Urban planners and policymakers, to align financial instruments with sustainability goals.
- Project developers, to structure investor-ready green projects.

The development of this Guide draws on a range of publicly available resources. The databases of financial instruments and case studies were informed by multiple existing catalogues, tools and studies. Key resources include the [Finance Guidance Tool](#), developed under the NetZeroCities project, and the [Financial Instruments Toolkit](#), developed by the Cities Climate Finance leadership Alliance (CCFLA). Additional sources include publications and data from the NAP Global Network, European Environment Agency (EEA), World Bank and others, all of which are referenced directly within the Guide. The collection, classification and analysis of data across all modules, including financial instruments, case studies and financing programmes was conducted by GGGI. Typologies and filter categories were developed to ensure consistency, comparability and practical usability across the tool.

4.4.2 [Structure of the tool](#)

The tool is organised into a series of modules:

- Core modules (Financial Instruments, Case Studies, Financing and Technical Assistance Programmes) are structured as searchable databases that allow users to filter, identify and explore options relevant to their context.
- Complementary modules provide high-level guidance and explanatory support, helping users understand how to navigate the broader climate finance landscape, structure appropriate financing approaches for their local context and engage with relevant stakeholders throughout the funding process.

Together, these modules aim to either support early-stage project planning or upscaling by helping cities identify appropriate financing strategies, key stakeholders and programmes and draw insights from real-world examples. Users can navigate the guide by filling out a central questionnaire that filters the core modules, based on their project needs. The filters are organised in two parts, as shown in the example of Figure 9:

- Investment project characterisation: Sector; Climate action type (filterable information for main modules).
- Module relevant filters as per different categories (check-boxes):
 - Financial Instruments: Instrument type; Modality; Source of finance; Category of blending; Instrument maturity; Investment readiness and risk.
 - Case Studies: Region; City size; Investment size; Type of case study.
 - International Financing and Technical Assistance Programmes: Type of assistance; Eligibility for EU Member States.

Green Finance Guide

Investment project characterization

Sector

- All sectors
- Transportation and mobility
- Buildings and energy efficiency
- Water, waste and wastewater
- Urban development and management
- Green spaces and nature-based solutions
- Disaster risk management

Climate action type

- Climate change mitigation and adaptation
- Climate change mitigation
- Climate change adaptation

Case studies

Region

- North America
- South America
- Europe
- Africa
- Asia
- Australia and Oceania

City size

- Multiple cities
- Mega (population >2M)
- Large (population 0.5M-2M)
- Medium (population 0.2M-0.5M)
- Small (population <0.2M)

Investment size

- Large (>300M EUR)
- Medium (50-300M EUR)
- Small (<50M EUR)

Figure 9: Overview of the filter system of the case studies module within the Green Finance Guide.

Users can select one or multiple options per category; more specific filtering (i.e., fewer selected options) will return more targeted results. Once filters are selected, users must click the "Submit" button to apply them. The tool provides the most suitable financing instruments and mechanisms per category, based on the input provided by the user.

4.4.3 Results

The Green Finance Guide responds to the following purposes:

- Cities become more familiar with green finance options and their applications.
- Improved access to a wide range of green financial instruments.
- Greater capacity for cities to fund and implement sustainable projects across multiple sectors.
- Municipalities develop investor-ready green project pipelines.
- Enhanced ability to tailor financial strategies to specific project needs.

The Green Finance Guide is strongly aligned with the objectives of the 5UP approach, as it plays a key role in the early planning stages of urban projects, enabling cities to:

- UPdate, by identifying available funding opportunities for green projects.
- UPscale, by securing financial support for expanding climate initiatives.

At both the pilot and upscaling phases, the guide provides insights into project readiness levels, investment risks and financial structuring strategies.

5 Connections with the UP2030 Upscaling Methodology

In line with the objective of supporting upscaling efforts in cities, the UP2030 Service Platform contains a section to provide the user with the necessary knowledge to develop an upscaling plan for its urban planning projects. On the one hand, information on the upscaling methodology developed in UP2030 for cities is provided, and on the other hand, practical examples of how this methodology has helped to create an upscaling plan for 10 cities are presented.

UP-Scaling: strengthen the governance conditions, institutional arrangements, financial frameworks and knowledge resources to expand project ideas, embed them in policy processes and maximise their long-term impact.

5.1 Upscaling methodology

The UP2030 project built an upscaling methodology to provide cities with instrument and resources developed during the project, so that the prototypes developed during the project can be grown and adapted to other sectors, regions and countries, in order to accomplish the goals defined by each city. This process ensures that best practices are transferable and adaptable across different urban contexts. This methodology was implemented by 10 cities and helped them on moving from a series of objectives to a concrete plan for upscaling and/or replicating the prototypes developed during the UP2030 project.

The success of the replication or upscaling efforts is completely reliant on the institutional environment in which the actions will be implemented. Therefore, in this process it is essential to create an “enabling environment”, as presented in the Section 1 of this document. In order to address the needs that cities have in relation to the pillars of governance and finance, cities were provided with the content collected in the tools developed by Adelphi and GGGI, which are now hosted in the Service Platform.

The upscale methodology in UP2030 was structured in three key phases: preparatory work with cities, engagement with the Learning and Action Alliance (LAA), and a follow-up phase focusing on transferability. The cities used a template to plan for the activities to be conducted in each phase, as well as to collect the main results from each step. This template is available in the Service Platform for cities that would like to implement the upscaling methodology of UP2030. The following sub-sections provide further details about these three phases of the methodology.

5.1.1 Preparatory work with cities and liaisons

The primary goal of this phase was to define the city-specific objectives with the cities, by conducting an initial consultation with city representatives to understand their local context, challenges and priorities. For this, cities and liaisons have worked on the pillars of the enabling environment for upscaling defined above. Thanks to a 1-hour workshop held with adelphi and GGGI, the cities:

- Explored the available tools on governance and finance that support upscaling (available in “Tools” section under the Service Platform).
- Understood the local context, challenges and priorities of cities.
- Defined the objectives for upscaling.

These points were the basis for guiding the conversation with local stakeholders during the LAA workshop.

5.1.2 Workshop with the Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs)

The second step was a workshop that each city organised individually with stakeholders of their LAAs. The LAAs are knowledge exchange and co-creation platforms intended to support the communication, coordination, innovation, and dialogue between city stakeholders at multiple levels.

The LAA workshop is the central piece of the upscaling methodology. Cities and their liaisons organised a half-a-day workshop with the relevant local stakeholders, with the purpose of:

- Setting the scene, presenting the objective and defining the resources and capacities to move forward.
- Creating readiness among the stakeholders at the local level.
- Designing an initial implementation plan for upscaling actions.

The completion of this workshop built a clear concept about upscaling and defined key next steps for moving from planning to implementation.

Figure 10. Pictures from the LAA workshops from Istanbul and Münster.

5.1.3 Follow-up workshop

The follow-up workshop was a debriefing session with ICLEI (who led the upscaling phase in the project) where cities and liaisons analysed the data collected from the LAA workshop and develop the Transferability Package, based on the insights and outcomes obtained in the workshop with the local stakeholders. The Transferability Package contains the following information:

- Definition of the objectives for the upscaling phase for the city, specifying which are the dimensions that will be addressed and the impact generated with the actions.
- List of barriers when it comes to upscaling and measures proposed to overcome these.
- Plan for upscaling the prototype, collecting the next steps for design and implementation and assigning roles and responsibilities among the actors involved.
- Guidance materials and resources to inform key stakeholders about the upscaling phase and the activities that need to be conducted.

5.2 Examples from UP2030 cities – Transferability Packages

One of the main outcomes that cities obtained from the upscaling methodology is the transferability package, which is designed to serve as a guidance document for cities to assist them in transitioning from the planning phase to the implementation phase of upscaling activities. The information that these Transferability Packages contain was defined in section 5.1.3. A transferability package has been created for each city that completed the upscale phase and they have been made available in the Service Platform under the [section “Upscaling for Cities”](#), so that the users of the platform can find

some real-life examples about how the upscaling methodology can be applied and how it helps to develop a plan for extending the impact of project ideas.

6 Dissemination and exploitation of the UP2030 Service Platform

6.1 Dissemination activities

The UP2030 Service Platform was officially launched in November 2025. Since then, various dissemination activities have been carried out to present the results and increase the platform's audience.

- The platform was first presented at the UP2030 Final Event titled “Cities in Action - Shaping just, resilient & climate neutral urban planning”, held in Barcelona on the 3rd of November of 2025. In this event, the partners involved in the development of the platform (ICLEI, adelphi, GreenAdapt and GGGI), together with the MOOC developer (UIC), organised a workshop focused on scaling up urban climate solutions for climate neutrality, where the participants could learn more about the practical tools, financial models and governance approaches that were created in the project to transform demonstrations into investable, city-wide interventions. The workshop offered a good opportunity to collect feedback of the overall structure of the platform and the tools hosted there.
- Within the same week as the final event, the Service Platform was disseminated at the stand that the UP2030 project had as part of the European Commission stand in the Smart Cities Expo World Congress, which also took place in Barcelona. QR codes of the platform were facilitated at the stand and in the workbook that was shared with the participants of the event. In addition, within the Smart Cities Expo, ICLEI participated in the session organised by the project coordinator, Fraunhofer, titled “Bridging Implementation Gaps: From Pilots to Systemic Action”. This session offered an opportunity to introduce the UP2030 Service Platform to the audience.
- In addition, the Service Platform was also presented at the last UP2030 Cities & Liaisons meeting, which takes place bi-monthly online, on the 24th of November. In this meeting, the Service Platform team had a dedicated slot to present to cities the overall structure of the platform, the tools that it contains and the way the platform contributes to upscaling objectives. Together with the Service Platform, an introduction to the MOOC was also provided in this meeting.
- The Service Platform was also shared with the entire consortium through the UP2030 internal newsletters in September and November, where partners received updates on developments to the Service Platform and the project's upscale phase.
- A [press release](#) was published on the UP2030 project website in November, in order to communicate the main results of the platform to the external audience.
- Furthermore, the Service Platform is currently being disseminated through the communication channels of platform partners to expand its reach. For instance, ICLEI featured the Service Platform in the Urban Resilience Newsletter published in December, which reached approximately 2200 subscribers.

6.2 Connections with other platforms and services

With the objective of increasing the visibility of the Service Platform and grow the number of people that will be using it, connections with other platforms will be established.

- On the one hand, a page for the Service Platform will be set in the UP2030 website, so that it is visible together with the rest of the tools and resources developed during the project.
- On the other hand, connections with the Net Zero Cities platform will be created, by adding the Service Platform in the [knowledge repository](#), together with other resources from UP2030 that have already been uploaded there (e.g., Citizen Mapping Tool, Toolkit for Stakeholder

Engagement towards Carbon Neutrality, etc.). Opportunities for organising webinars on trainings for cities that are connected to Net Zero Cities will be explored. These trainings would be focused on finance, taking as reference the CBA Guide and the Green Finance Guide.

- In addition, this deliverable will be uploaded to [Zenodo](#). The document and therefore the Service Platform itself will be accessible through this platform.
- Lastly, ICLEI and Fraunhofer are currently exploring the options for bringing the platform to the Smart Cities Marketplace, together with other results produced in the project.

6.3 Future development / exploitation

For the purpose of maintaining the Service Platform usable and updated, and for ensuring that it will be impactful after a certain period of time after the project ends, an exploitation plan for the platform has been designed, which is collected in D6.9 (Jelmini & Dommerholt, 2025) developed by the Institute for Urban Excellence. Many of the key actions for exploitation have been defined in the Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) that the partners involved in the development of the platform (see Section 2.2) signed. This MoU outlines the intention of the partners to sustain, promote, and further develop the UP2030 Service Platform beyond the end of the project, in alignment with the project's mission of enabling climate-neutral and just urban transitions.

This MoU outlines the objectives and planned actions related to the sustainability and operation of the Service Platform, along with the roles and responsibilities of all organisations involved in its development. The document does not constitute a legally binding agreement, as the parties currently lack the financial and human resources needed to guarantee the implementation of the actions described. Nevertheless, the document seeks to provide a foundation for collaboration among the parties (see Section 2) and to support the exploration of future opportunities for the ongoing development and maintenance of the UP2030 Service Platform.

The main actions that are collected in the MoU can be categorised in two groups:

- Actions for communicating and disseminating the results. All partners have agreed on using their best effort to communicate the results collected on the Service Platform by using different channels, in order to increase the platform's impact by reaching a wider audience.
- Actions for developing the platform and its resources. Since there will be no human and financial resources available once the project is finalised, which makes it impossible to guarantee that any action for continuing developing the platform can be carried out, all partners undertake to actively seek funding opportunities and further collaboration opportunities. These actions encompass preparing a proposal for a Horizon call that features a dedicated work package for the platform, incorporating the platform and/or the tools described in Section 4 into ongoing projects, among other possible activities.

In addition, the MoU establishes the basis for collaboration among partners, by defining how the ownership of the results will be managed and assigning specific roles that each partner could take (in case funding opportunities will be found) for ensuring that the platform is updated and enhanced, and meets user's needs after the end of the project.

7 Conclusion

The UP2030 Services Platform serves to provide a space where cities can find methodologies and solutions to help them scale up the urban planning project ideas they have developed. In this way, the platform moves away from being simply a repository of tools and provides a specific ‘service’ that is a key step not only for the cities that have participated in the project, but also for other cities facing the same challenge of increasing the impact of their actions in urban planning and continuing the work they have done.

As it is directly related to the upscaling phase, the Service Platform aligns with the narrative of the 5UP methodology, thus providing continuity to the work carried out in previous phases of the project with cities, where needs have been analysed, a project vision created and a prototype developed. All of this is reflected in the platform and, with the inclusion of the 5UP Workbook, a space is provided where users can navigate through the phases prior to upscaling and receive guidance on developing their project ideas that promote the sustainable development of their cities.

The platform has been designed to offer solutions to different types of challenges in different local contexts. The Urban Typologies tool plays a key role in this, as it analyses the characteristics of European regions in terms of urban planning, climate neutrality and climate change adaptation, and seeks to establish a basis for promoting collaboration between different regions and providing a series of recommendations to help regions and cities identify strategies relevant to their context and address climate challenges effectively.

Following this line of thought, the platform also aims to reinforce the strategic vision for the future of cities, providing tools that address financial aspects and organisational structures, which are two of the essential pillars for creating the enabling environment necessary to carry out upscaling actions. The third pillar, which focuses on capacity building among local actors, is covered by the MOOC, which is connected to the platform through links that direct users to learning modules on key concepts, tools and case studies.

Furthermore, it is important to show on the platform that all the tools provided are not only theoretical, but can also be applied in a real context. This is demonstrated by the transferability packages from the 10 cities that have implemented the upscaling methodology in the project. By defining the objectives for upscaling and analysing the barriers and opportunities that exist in their local context, cities have been able to design a plan for the future that gives continuity to the work carried out in the project and highlights the important role that the prototype can play in the city's sustainable development planning. These examples from UP2030 cities also aim to serve as a mirror for other cities that come to the platform, providing examples of how to develop an upscaling plan and the key aspects to consider.

Thanks to all these resources, the UP2030 Service Platform becomes a robust framework that can be implemented in different contexts, with the aim of creating sustainable, resilient and fair cities. To this end, it is crucial to increase the platform's reach, and the performance of the partners involved in dissemination and exploitation tasks will play a key role in this. Looking ahead, there is a strong willingness on the part of the partners to continue working on improving and developing the platform, as demonstrated in the MoU that has been created to lay the foundations for collaboration and responsibilities among the partners involved.

As for the future development of the platform, it would be willing to host additional resources from other projects or initiatives that are aligned with the goal of upscaling, as well as to raise the quality of existing resources based on the contributions and experiences gained from those projects. Ultimately, for a product to remain useful in the market, it must be able to respond to the needs of the user (in this case, cities), and in the current context where the geopolitical and climate scenario is so variable, the platform should also be able to offer solutions to emerging challenges of the future.

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